

USING THE LEGACY OF OUR GREAT ANCESTORS IN ELEMENTARY READING LESSONS

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Annotation: in this article, the author reflected on delivery to the reader intelligibly, using themes related to the personality and works of past thinkers in shaping the reader's spiritual worldview.

Keywords. Volitional person, educator, reader, style, literacy, interactive, modern pedagogical technologies.

Special attention is paid to the study of historical, national, spiritual values in the content of socio-economic, spiritual and religious changes carried out in Uzbekistan. One of the necessary conditions for human spiritual maturation, which Eastern thinkers such as Abu Nasr Farabi, Abu Ali ibn Sina, Beruniy, Kaykovus recognized, is independent and logical thinking. In this process, the reader shows excellent activity, creativity, initiative. The study of the work of our allies, Beruniy, Farabi, Abu Ali ibn Sina, Mahmud Qoshgariy, Yusuf Khos Hajib and others, who made their unique contributions to our cultural heritage, has great educational value for the future generation. Each of them contributed to the development of world civilization. The name of Joseph the specific Pilgrim in this range can also be mentioned with pride and pride. "Qutadgü bilig" by Yusuf Khos Hajib and "Devani lexicotit-turk" by Mahmud Qoshgari are among the masterpieces of spirituality. At this point, it is not accidental that we use the word "qomusiy". Each created Work educates the reader, the reader in one direction.

"Qutadg'g bilig", on the other hand, emerged as an ambitious work that embodied the way of governing the state, its politics, its legacies, its painting, its moral principles. The work has a didactic orientation, in which the methods of governing the state, from the common people to the elixirs of higher ranks — such as a scientist, poet, peasant, rancher, poor—are described in terms of what the character of many classes, categories, social groups should be, state construction, the place and importance of various social classes in society, in general, political-social, material Joseph Khos Hajib was a wise man, thinker, progressive-minded philosopher of his time. In his work, he approaches science, knowledge, and intelligence with special attention: a person without knowledge collects without a feed, and a non-absorbent collects" neku qilsu ach. (The ignorant is a fruitless Wood, the fruitless Wood is what the Hungry Man does). The fact that these expressions are compact, succulent, cordially creamy attracts attention. The fluency of expression, the naturalness of the phenomenon being mentioned, the fact that it is closely connected directly with everyday life also increases its power of influence. The task of educating elementary students as a spiritually-morally competent, educated person is in many ways interconnected with the correct Organization of education in elementary grades, in particular, teaching students to think independently, growing their speech at the level of demand. It is natural for a rich reader to have a wide range of thinking, a high spirituality, a high passion for reading and learning. Through reading lessons in elementary grades, literacy qualities are formed in students, a sense of love for a book is awakened, their knowledge of the environment is expanded, speech and thinking are increased. In speech Education, "text" is also a central concept. After all, the ultimate goal of work on the development of speech in a general secondary school is to teach the student to freely state his opinion in oral and written form. The child is impressive at a young age, becomes a quick recipient of all the information coming from around him. What he hears, he seeks to pronounce as he hears and apply it, in his

speech. Therefore, from the very beginning of the school year of elementary students, it is necessary to determine the scope of speech, take measures to eliminate speech defects and work on them. Vocabulary sets the stage for the rapid and thorough mastery of the knowledge given to students from all disciplines and the mastery of skills and skills provided for in educational programs.

On the ground of students ' demand to improve their reading skills, improve their literacy, grow their speech, a culture of speech stands. In the spiritual maturation of children, special importance has long been attached to the culture and etiquette of speech. Therefore, practical tasks aimed at growing students ' speech should be solved. In this context, the first to give a 1st grade reading book through the "generation of us-greats" section is an instructive text about the "Amir Temur" grandfather of the writer Muhammad Ali, followed by the Amir Temur ögitlar, which is clearly and intelligibly told to readers. When passing the topics in the section, we can use the following methods. Readers should remember the names of great thinkers: Alisher Navoi, Husayn Boyqaro, Abu Ali ibn Sina, Mirza Ulugbek, Babur Mirza and Amir Temur. If we shape the spiritual worldview of students from the initial grade, then first of all we need to take into account their interests, the level of knowledge. It is known that primary school students are 7-11 years old, while their interest in playing activities is 75-80 percent. At the same time, when raising the spiritual worldview of students and bringing them to adulthood as a harmonious person, it is necessary to pay attention to the following statement: — to teach subjects, spiritual concepts in a closely related way when students grow the spiritual worldview. - extensive use of topics related to the works of past thinkers given in reading lessons in the formation of a spiritual worldview and delivery to the reader in an understandable way. - finding measures to achieve students ' mastery of topics, independent thinking. - creative approach to each lesson. - the appropriate and purposeful use of various methods,

interactive methods, advanced pedagogical technologies in the lesson. - interest students in learning and mastering the subject with various didactic games. - from methodological innovations and pedagogical experiments, it is always bokhabar to apply them to the educational process.

In conclusion, it is possible to say that in elementary grades, the foundation of knowledge obtained through reading lessons, which are the leading subjects of school education, will be built. The most appropriate, most convenient methods and methods, proper and purposeful use of advanced pedagogical technologies in the cultivation of the spiritual worldview of students, provide effective results in the work of reading and teaching. The joint creative activity of educators and students facilitates the assimilation of topics.

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